

Design and Structural Analysis of a Semi-Trailer Chassis

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Abstract: The Chantier Naval Industriel du Cameroun (CINC), an autonomous entity within the Office National des Ports du Cameroun (ONPC), is aligned with the Cameroonian Government's long-term development initiative, "Cameroon Vision 2035," aiming for national emergence by 2035. This paper presents the design and sizing of a robust chassis for semi-trailers intended to transport goods weighing up to 27 tons, with the following specifications: payload capacity of 27,000 kg, overall length of 12,350 mm, and overall width of 2,500 mm. Our dimensioning adheres to internationally recognized standards and regulatory codes, including ABS (Construction and Classification Rules for Metal Construction Barges), EUROCODE 3 (Calculation of Steel Structures), and BS EN ISO 12944 (Protection of Metal Surfaces). These standards provide the foundation for the structural characteristics necessary for steel construction. To achieve our objectives, we employed various analytical tools, including the QQQCCP method, the OCTOPUS diagram, and the horned beast digraph. Numerical analyses were performed using SOLIDWORKS software to validate the design. The estimated cost of the project is 4,813,798.18 CFA francs. Our analysis using Ansys software revealed that the structure would fail under the 27-ton load due to specific structural weaknesses. However, the analysis performed with SOLIDWORKS software concluded that our structure fully meets the service suitability conditions and can be safely deployed once installed on-site. Detailed results of these analyses are discussed in the subsequent sections of this paper.

Keywords: structural design, chassis, semi-trailer, Cameroon Vision 2035, SOLIDWORKS

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Introduction

The Industrial Union for Cameroon (UIC), wholly owned by the Chantier Naval Industriel du Cameroun (CNIC) since October 2003, has a rich history dating back to its creation in 1964 by the UIE group. It was subsequently acquired by the French group Bouygues Offshore in 1984. As part of its strategic development and in preparation for transforming the Limbe Oil Yard into a significant industrial hub, CNIC initiated an operation aimed at horizontal integration. This strategic move is aligned with the broader vision of "Cameroon Vision 2035," which aims for national emergence and industrialization by 2035. In addition to its primary activities of repairing ships, mobile oil platforms, and undertaking industrial works, CNIC has incorporated UIC's expertise in repairing fixed offshore oil platforms and industrial works. Expanding its scope, CNIC now aims to diversify its operations by establishing a business unit focused on the

automotive sector, specifically for the development of semi-trailers designed to transport goods and machinery up to a mass of 27 tons. This diversification marks a significant expansion into the industrial works sector, reflecting the dynamic and evolving industrial landscape of Cameroon. The primary hypothesis driving this study is that the development of a robust and optimally sized semi-trailer chassis can significantly enhance the transportation infrastructure necessary for supporting Cameroon's industrial growth. This study focuses on ensuring the stability and safety of the semi-trailer chassis through optimal sizing and load distribution. By adhering to internationally recognized standards and leveraging advanced analytical tools, we aim to model and size a semi-trailer chassis that meets specified requirements and supports the nation's strategic objectives. This research is crucial as it not only contributes to the diversification and growth of CNIC's operations but also supports the overarching goal of industrialization under the "Cameroon Vision 2035" initiative. Through this study, we seek to provide a comprehensive solution that aligns with global standards and addresses the current needs of Cameroon's industrial sector.

Materials and Methods

This chapter outlines the tools and methods utilized to carry out the study. It includes the dimensional analysis performed using software, the presentation of equipment, and the methods applied to construct the structure based on specific requirements and material types. The specifications provided by the CNIC, which guide the need to broaden its field of activity and establish an automotive business unit, are crucial to this analysis. Technical Specifications Table 5 presents the technical specifications of the trailer:

Weight and dimensions	Gross Vehicle Weight: Payload + Curb Weight Payload: 27000 Kg Overall length: 12350mm Overall width: 2500 m Curb weight : 290.83024 Kg
Chassis	- In high-strength steel consisting of 02 mechanically welded spars with an "T" section braced by stamped crossbeams. ISO 1726 Standardized Gooseneck
Plateau	Steel floor 12 side panels + rear door Reinforced and easily removable front tailgate - 12 twist-locks for containers (one 40 feet, two 20 feet and one 20 feet centered), mounted in reinforced tubular arms.
Device of coupling	2-inch linchpin, interchangeable
Running gear	BPW brand tandem type, consisting of: Mechanical suspension with six multi-leaf springs in steel Three axles, tubular body, made of steel, ground load 17 tons Drum brake controlled by S-cam. Twin tyre mounting, on 22.5 x 9 rim.
Lighting and signage	- Complete VIGNAL lighting and signage in accordance with the highway code. Voltage 24 V- 2 sockets, 7 ISO pins. Lighting composed of: 7-function tail lights Side marker lights Two front position lights in white

Crutches	Mark Manually operated 2-speed telehandler. Lifting capacity: 27 tons
Accessories	Anti-underride bumper at the back. Half fender on rear wheel with splash-proof rubber mud flap. Plastic water tank capacity 50 liters. Side cycle guard, liftable in aluminium. A double spare wheel support with winch. A plastic toolbox Wheel Lever Wrench Hub remover wrench 2 wheel chocks Instructions for use and maintenance
Surface treatment and painting	Shot blasting of the steel parts of the structure. A coat of two-component primer paint. Two coats of finish; Colour to be specified: at the customer's choice.

Functional analysis.

Functional analysis is central to the design process, essential for both creating and improving products. This approach identifies and defines the service functions associated with a product, facilitating the development of technical solutions. By identifying, characterizing, organizing, and prioritizing these functions, functional analysis aims to enhance the quality of the product or service by focusing primarily on its fundamental functions. The analysis of the need is based on 3 main steps

Figure 1: The analysis of the need.

External Functional Analysis

The service function defines what is expected from a product to meet the user's needs, whether material, physiological, psychological, or socio-cultural. It is expressed as $FS = FP + FC$ (FS: service function, FP: main function, FC: constraint function), using an action verb in the infinitive followed by one or more complements. The main function highlights the relationships created by the product within its external environment and justifies its creation. The constraint function, on the other hand, expresses specific requirements that limit the designer's freedom. To determine these functions, we will illustrate the equipment within its external environment using an octopus diagram, highlighting the relevant functions. Internal Functional Analysis In this phase, we will analyze the mechanism internally, identifying various technological solutions to realize the technical functions, main functions, and constraints. For the development of our semi-trailer, the essential elements include: Undercarriage (Axles): Each axle is identified by a plate containing information such as axle brand, type, production number, test report number, maximum permissible static axle mass, and maximum speed allowed. Wheels and Tyres: The characteristics of the tyres are indicated on the casing, with the

brand and type on the first line, and technical characteristics such as tyre width, nominal aspect ratio, radial structure, rim diameter, single-fit load capacity index, twin load capacity index, and speed rating on the second and third lines.

Suspension:Trailer suspensions are generally of the rigid type made of steel with non-independent stamping, consisting of tandem leaf springs and suspension bearing components.

Braking System:The vehicle's braking function is managed by various pneumatic and/or electrical components, which may vary depending on the vehicle's options. Braking is controlled electro-pneumatically via the EBS braking system, with power supplied through the "ABS" socket (ISO 7638).

Crutch:The legs have two speeds: high speed for quickly extending and retracting the inner tube when the semi-trailer is attached, and low speed for lifting the semi-trailer when the legs touch the ground. The stands are equipped with lubrication, requiring no maintenance for three years. Afterward, they must be checked for wear and lubricated annually.

Wheel Carriers:Installed under the chassis, wheel carriers allow the storage of one or two spare wheels, positioned either at the rear or side of the vehicle.

Tool Chest:Intended for storing tools or other necessary equipment for transport.

Anti-Spray Systems:These systems, consisting of a specific energy-absorbing coating placed behind and above the wheels, significantly reduce water splashes when driving on wet roads.

Side Protections:Installed under the bodywork, side guards protect pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists from entering the side of the vehicle. Tool and pallet boxes under the body are part of this protection system. Some models are retractable to allow access to auxiliary equipment.

Rear Underride Bar:This safety device protects road users in case of a rear impact. It must not be removed or modified and, if a tailgate lift is attached, it can serve as an underride bar if approved for this purpose.

Product EnvironmentThis step involves inventorying all factors that can influence our system in its external environment. For our project, these factors include geometry, cost, security, various obstacles, standards, ergonomics, maintenance, and operators.

Product Environment Diagram: Octopus DiagramThe octopus diagram, or interaction diagram, elaborates the relationship between a product or service and its environment, highlighting its main and complementary functions. In this diagram, the product or service is at the center, with external elements around it, connected by lines according to their roles.

Figure 2: Octopus diagram. [12]

Table 6: Formulation of service functions.

DUTIES	EXPRESSIONS
FP	Diversify the scope of the CNIC and increase its re- Come
F1	Ensuring comfort for the driver and the goods
F2	Have a geometry corresponding to the space allocated to it
F3	Comply with building standards
F4	To make the stage, the beams... Uniforms at the limit of what is possible
F5	Take into account the cross-sections and strength of the profiles chosen.

F6	Be within the reach of the customer (user).
F7	Resist corrosion
F8	Respect ergonomics

II-1-2-5) Formulation of service functions.

III-2-2) Problematic and objective. The CNIC plans to find a new design for a rolling trail runner for the creation of its Automobile business unit, for the transport of heavy goods. The system must meet the following conditions:- To allow the user to transport and control goods safely;- Have a system that is reliable in operation;- Ensure the effectiveness and plausibility of the trail runner;- Ensure the reliability of the results.II-2-3) The QQQQCP method.

What?	Have a trail runner who can support a load of 27 tons
Who?	CNIC
Where?	CNIC
When?	The relaunch of the CNIC's activities
How?	Trailer Design
What for?	For the establishment of a business unit at the CNIC

Proposed solution :

First, we started by making a diagnosis of the various semi-towing platforms currently on the market in order to enrich our knowledge. After consulting various sites specializing in this field, we proposed a trail runner. Designed for the transport of goods weighing 27 tons.

The diagram of the horned beast.

The horned beast diagram allows us to define the *raison d'être* of a system, in our case it is the device to move the machines to the production unit lathe in pit.

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